

Applying Network Analysis and Feature Engineering in Machine Learning Models for Solar Forecasting

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1 Abstract

Solar flare and Coronal Mass Ejection (CME) prediction helps us protect delicate systems on Earth and in space. The causes of solar storms are not understood well enough to predict solar flares from preceding factors, so researchers are using advanced machine learning techniques to learn complex interactions and accurately predict solar flares. Part of these advanced techniques is synthesizing data from instrument readings to improve machine learning models using feature engineering.

In my thesis, I focused on full-disk analysis to create novel features for use in machine learning models to predict solar flares. I applied network analysis to explore the ways active regions influence each other and to analyze the efficacy of using full-disk features for solar prediction. Through this analysis, I computed features and compared their effectiveness both using statistical tests and by training basic neural networks.

2 Introduction

In 1859, a massive solar storm caused brilliant auroras all over Earth, even as far down as the tropics. Telegraph systems around the world shocked their operators from the induced current caused by charged particles thrown off by the sun. If a similar event occurred today, the damage to delicate electrical systems, power grids, and satellites would be incalculable[1].

These solar storms are called Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs), and they are closely related to solar flares occurring within Active Regions (ARs) on the Solar surface (the photosphere)[2]. A CME usually occurs after a large solar flare and results in a strong stream of charged particles that cause the Earth's magnetic field to oscillate and induce currents in wires on the ground[1].

Ultimately, an accurate and reliable system for analyzing solar data and predicting solar flares and CMEs will help protect Earth's delicate systems and provide additional information to keep astronauts in orbit safe from dangerous radiation. The relatively new field of deep learning provides promising results for accurate prediction.

The mechanisms that cause solar flares are not understood well enough to use science to predict them accurately. Prediction models are largely divided into two categories: statistical methods and machine learning methods. The current system for flare prediction is a statistical one. It classifies sunspots

in a system called *McIntosh classifications*, and then calculates the probability of a solar event based on prior results for that classification [3]. This system depends on a person to classify a sunspot, and these classifications depend on subjective characteristics including symmetry, the existence of a penumbra, and the distribution of spots [4]. This system cannot capture the full complexity of an AR, and yet its accuracy is comparable to most other models, even those using advanced machine learning. Regardless of technique, no models have been able to get results significantly better than random, despite using techniques which proved successful for prediction in many other fields[5].

A supervised machine learning algorithm takes in data (features) and results (labels), and produces a model that takes in data and makes a forecast. They do not have a scientific backing beyond what data is put in. Existing machine learning methods use parameters derived from ARs, such as the flux or area, rather than analyzing raw magnetograms. These measurements clearly lack parameters that are necessary for prediction, as machine learning models using them have not improved upon the McIntosh method [5]. In addition, these prediction methods use snapshots of data, rather than features capturing the evolution of an AR, despite research showing the importance of evolution to solar flare prediction[6]. At best, the feature sets include a few basic features intended to capture some of this evolution, such as the history of flares within a given AR[6].

I created several features from solar data to improve prediction accuracy by determining important quantities which are predictive of the likelihood of a solar flare. These features are based on full-disk data, which uses all the ARs visible on the solar surface to aid prediction in a novel method of analysis. I analyzed these features to determine importance, allowing an increased scientific understanding as well as improved model creation.

In my approach, rather than depending on scientific quantities derived from solar measurements, I applied abstract analysis to create new features. This approach allowed me to break away from existing understanding of AR dynamics, which seems to be insufficient for building accurate prediction methods. Instead, I focused on how multiple active regions interact with each other, using network analysis to compare relationships and to model interactions in a simplistic way. Finally, I looked at how the physical location of an AR affects the probability of flaring.

The creation of an accurate and reliable system for anticipating solar flares would help us protect against the large storms that affect GPS, radar, and

electrical systems [1]. A warning system would prevent confusion and allow the controllers of delicate satellites and sensitive equipment that could be damaged by a large solar storm to take the necessary precautions. An effective system could also help increase the knowledge of the phenomena that indicate solar flares, and guide future scientific exploration into the exact causes of solar flares.

3 Background

To apply feature engineering to this problem, I combined information from several different disciplines, including machine learning and data analysis, network science, and solar science and physics. To conduct this analysis, I created features from solar data and used networks to analyze full-disk data from all ARs.

3.1 Causes of Solar Flares and CMEs

On the Sun's surface (called the photosphere), sunspots and ARs are caused by magnetic energy pushing through the hot plasma. Every sunspot is in an AR, and most solar flares originate from these areas of magnetic activity. Sunspots are connected by a loop of magnetic energy called a filament that stretches from inside the Sun into its atmosphere (the corona)[1]. This phenomenon cannot be observed directly, so all filament data is calculated using theoretical models[7].

Solar flares are a burst of magnetic energy expelled from an AR when the filament gains enough energy to twist, snap, and reconnect[2]. Solar flares are composed of X-ray light, which affects radio waves and poses a danger to any astronauts who are unprotected by Earth's magnetic field [1]. X-rays also cause an expansion of the Earth's ionosphere, which can slow down satellites and cause them to change their orbits and even "get lost" during large solar storms [1].

A CME is a burst of high-energy particles which affect the Earth's magnetic field and cause the Aurora[2]. CMEs are usually preceded by large solar flares, although there have been CMEs from relatively low-energy flares[7]. These two solar phenomena are found to be linked very closely, although it is not well understood what causes either, or why there are strong flares without a corresponding CME[7]. If a CME hits Earth, the magnetic field of Earth oscillates, inducing current in electronics and shorting out sensitive equipment.

3.2 Solar Data

For any forecasting model, enough data is required for training and validation. The primary source of data for solar prediction comes from the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO), which has provided continuous solar data since 2010. In particular, the Heliospheric Magnetic Imager (HMI) instrument records the magnetic field at the solar surface, and thus is used to track and investigate active regions (ARs) on the solar surface[8]. The HMI instrument observes the entire solar disk, and automatically isolates ARs and labels them so they can be tracked. This data is returned as *magnetograms*, which are basically images that have recorded the magnetic field strength on the Photosphere at each pixel. There are two kinds of magnetograms returned from HMI. While *line of sight* magnetograms measure the Sun as we see it, *vector* magnetograms record the magnetic field as three separate components[8]. Vector magnetograms save magnetic strength in westward, radial, and southward components for a more complete analysis of magnetic energy [8]. For each recorded time, HMI provides one image for the line of sight magnetogram and three images for the vector magnetogram.

The HMI team identifies ARs in a HMI Active Region Patches (HARPs) series by automatically finding magnetically complex sections in the magnetograms of the full solar disk [8]. Each AR is uniquely identified with a HARP number. NOAA also identifies and labels ARs, although they use a different system with different numbers. HARP numbers can be mapped to NOAA ARs to combine these two data sets, so the X-ray flux data recorded by NOAA can be tracked to a specific AR found by HMI. The HMI team also computes numerical summary statistics on each recorded active region and collects them in a data series known as Spaceweather HMI Active Region Patches (SHARPs)[8]. This data includes information like the total flux, the mean shear angle, and other similar data points for a given AR.

Finally, some prediction research includes data from the Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) instrument on SDO. This instrument studies the Sun's corona by taking full-disk images in different wavelengths [8]. Data from this instrument is used to study affects from the solar atmosphere on flaring regions.

In order to label this data, we also need to know when an AR had a flare, which is not measured by HMI. This information is recorded by the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) X-ray flux instruments, which returns the NOAA AR number, the time, and the X-ray flux of each solar flare.

We match the flare data to the HMI data using the NOAA AR number, and can then classify each flare using the flux data. Thus, we can label our HMI data with when a flare occurred, and the strength of the flare, which provides us with the initial features and labels required for training a machine learning model.

3.3 Networks

A network or graph is a way of structuring data for analysis. Particularly, networks represent relationships between entities. A network consists of nodes and edges. The nodes are the actual objects whose relationships are represented, and the edges represent those relationships.

The edges in a network can be weighted to contain additional information about relationships between nodes. For example, a weighted graph between cities with edges representing roads could have weights that represent the size of those roads.

A *fully-connected* network is one where every node is connected to every other node. On the other hand, a *partially connected* network has nodes which are not connected by edges. If two nodes can be reached by following along other edges through other nodes, such as how two cities can be connected through other cities, then these two nodes are connected by a *path*, and are in the same *component*. A component is described as a subgraph in which any two nodes are connected by a path. If there are paths between all nodes in the graph, it is one component, but if there are any nodes that cannot reach another part of the graph by following edges, there are at least two components.

When analyzing networks, we can look at the *structural importance* of a given node within the graph as a whole. Structural importance is based on using only the structure of a graph, instead of looking at a dynamic system running on the network [9]. While dynamic analysis involves looking at the flow of information through the network, structural analysis only looks at the static shape of the network. One way of analyzing structure is by computing the *centrality* of a node. A highly centralized node has an important role in transmitting information through a network.

A highly centralized node can be defined by its *degree*, or the number of edges connected to the node [9]. Nodes that have a higher degree are connected to more of the network, and therefore the degree of a node can indicate its influence within the graph.

However, a degree focuses on local importance, rather than global importance of a node within the structure of a network. Another way to compute importance is to compare the importance of a node to that of its neighbors, so that a node has increased importance if it is also connected to important nodes in the network[9]. To calculate this, we recursively update importance of nodes in the network until they converge. *Eigenvector centrality* computes the convergence of the recursive importance calculation through computing the principle eigenvector of the adjacency matrix[9]. Eigenvector centrality allows us to compute the importance of a node in a network by designating important areas in the structure of the network and by assigning additional importance to nodes which are highly-connected to important nodes.

3.4 Machine Learning

The goal for a machine learning model is generally to take in input data and make a prediction based on previous results. A machine learning algorithm uses a large set of data points, where each data point can consist of multiple pieces of information, called *features*. An example of a feature is the total magnetic flux of a given AR at a given time point. Each set of features is labelled with if there was a flare or not, and the strength of the flare.

The data is split into a training set and a validation set. The machine learning algorithm takes in data from the training set, and uses that to modify itself in order to "learn" how to predict the correct labels. Then, the validation data is used to analyze the results and measure performance. During validation, the model is held static as it predicts data points from the validation set. The output for each data point is compared to the actual label to analyze the effectiveness of the model.

Although the basic principles are the same, there are many different kinds of machine learning models. Prior research into solar flare prediction primarily uses machine learning methods such as support vector machines (SVM), K-nearest neighbors (KNN), and random forests. An SVM trains itself on a nonlinear split between data points, where every data point on one side of the divider is classified as positive and the other as negative. A KNN algorithm classifies based on the weighted distance to similar objects. This classifies points based on their similarity to points in the training data. A random forest algorithm trains many small decision trees, which divide the data set in two based on different criteria, and then combines them into a full classifier.

Another commonly used machine learning model is known as a neural net. This kind of machine learning is similar to the way a brain operates. A basic multi-layer perceptron (MLP) model has layers consisting of perceptrons. A perceptron is a binary classifier which uses learned weights to output a one or a zero. A fully trained model takes the feature set and passes it through many layers of perceptrons, before processing it through an output function. A deep neural net can have hundreds of layers, so even a simple classifier like a perceptron can be combined with hundreds of others to create high complexity models.

My own prior work has focused on deep multi-layer perceptron (MLP) neural networks, recurrent neural nets (RNNs), and convolutional neural nets (CNNs). A RNN is a type of neural net that takes previous data points into account by passing through a "state" as part of its feature set. This allows the model to use previous outputs as part of training, thus using a historical record as part of the data. A convolutional neural net is a specialized model for analyzing image data, which is based on condensing and filtering data from images. All of these models used hundreds of layers for processing.

These deep learning methods were created with increases in computational power, and can train an extremely complicated model. This increased complexity also makes it hard to track the exact causes of certain predictions. In a decision tree, which splits the data in half each step depending on a binary classification it is simple to go through and see how the data was split up. With a neural net, this comparison is obfuscated underneath the math that calculates the importance of different features. This limitation can be compensated for with feature engineering and feature analysis. Feature analysis is a way of looking at the features within your model to determine the most important ones. This can allow insight into what is causing the actual phenomenon your model

is classifying - in this case, important features can show scientific reasons why certain ARs flare. Feature engineering is a method for creating new features for use in the model - and feature analysis and model comparison can show the effectiveness of those features.

3.5 Feature Engineering

To effectively improve machine learning models once we hit the limits of raw data, feature engineering is used to create new features based on external scientific knowledge or additional analysis of the data. If a feature is highly correlated with flaring data points, there is probably something physical causing the flares that is described by that feature. Thus, feature engineering is useful for scientific exploration as well as the creation of machine learning models. On the other hand, if we know that there is a phenomenon that is correlated with a solar flare, we can use feature engineering to make a feature to describe it, and improve our model that way.

In this case, since I am looking at images, feature engineering can reduce the complex image data into a few scalar data points. Just analyzing the raw images pixel-by-pixel would result in a feature set of 65536 for a 256x256 sized image. A model that large is past the limits of current computational power. Most image analysis is done using a Convolutional Neural Net (CNN), which *convolves* the image data down to important chunks that can then be analyzed. This method learns what features are important in an image, but in doing so, it abstracts them beyond the point of usefulness. On the other hand, feature engineering calculates important data more deliberately, and the best features for prediction can also be used to describe the scientific causes of solar flares.

To conduct analysis on features, statistical tests are applied to positive and negative data sets. If a feature is very different for positive and negative data sets, it provides a lot of information to the model, and is therefore more useful. To determine this value, an F-test analysis is applied to the data set. An F-test is used to determine if two samples both came from populations with similar variances, which also indicates if the means of the two populations are different [10]. If the F-test is far from 1, the two samples came from populations with different variances. The F-test can be calculated with the following formula [10]

$$F = \frac{S_1^2}{S_2^2}$$

where S_1^2 is the variance of sample 1:

$$S^2 = \sum \frac{(x - \bar{x})^2}{(n - 1)}$$

To rank all features, we calculate the F-test and determine the difference in flaring and non-flaring populations, which can show their usefulness within the model.

3.6 Model Evaluation

To determine the effectiveness of a machine learning model, sections of the total data are withheld from the training data. The trained model makes predictions on the validation data so the accuracy of the predictions can be assessed. There are a few ways to compare the model data to the validation data, with the most common being accuracy. This intuitive evaluation metric looks at the percentage of the model guesses that were correct. However, this will not be an effective measure in this problem. Solar flare data is very unbalanced, as the vast majority of data points do not have a flare. This means a model that predicts "No" for every data point would still have an accuracy of 0.98.

To get around this imbalance, there are evaluation methods that instead depend on the ratios of True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP) and False Negatives (FN). In particular, *skill scores* compare the accuracy of the results to a reference point, rather than accuracy, making them useful for imbalanced data sets[5]. This reference point can be things like a predictor that guesses at random or a predictor that always predicts "true" or "false"[5]. If a skill score calculation returns Skill = 1, then the predictor is perfect, and if it returns Skill = 0, then it is no better than the reference predictor[5].

A general skill score looks like the following:

$$Skill = \frac{A_{forecast} - A_{reference}}{A_{perfect} - A_{reference}} \quad (1)$$

Here, $A_{forecast}$ describes the accuracy of the model, $A_{reference}$ describes the accuracy of the reference method, and $A_{perfect}$ describes the accuracy of a perfect predictor[5]. For binary forecasting, like the kind I am doing, the perfect accuracy is 1 and the forecast accuracy is the rate correct[5]:

$$A_{forecast} = \frac{TP + TN}{N} \quad (2)$$

Where N is the number of data points in the validation set.

An Appleman Skill Score (ApSS) compares the model results to an unskilled predictor as a reference[5]. This reference predictor always predicts "false," as this is the most common result from flare forecasting.

$$A_{reference} = \frac{TN + FP}{N} \quad (3)$$

This allows us to see if the model is actually better than an unskilled predictor.

Another common skill score is the True Skill Score (TSS), also known as Hanssen and Kuipers' Discriminant [5]. In TSS, unskilled predictors (as used in (3)) and random predictors both score a zero, with perfect prediction as a 1. This skill score compares the ratio of positive prediction to that of negative prediction with the following [5]:

$$TSS = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} - \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (4)$$

TSS is a commonly used score in flaring prediction, and therefore will be the one I will be using to compare models. However, it is very important to note that TSS depends heavily on the threshold used to define a positive vs negative event. In addition, it is pointless to compare models that use different data sets for training or validation, as the differences between their skill scores could depend entirely on that aspect.

4 Previous Work

Much of the prior work for flare forecasting used simple machine learning methods. Many also started with SHARPs data, although there were several researchers that calculated their own features from magnetograms. Since the methods differ so greatly, it is difficult to compare individual models, but by looking at several papers, it is possible to develop intuition for the current state of the field.

Within the field of solar flare prediction, it is important to have a distinction between research work and operational work - that is, if the model is only for

feature engineering and analysis, or if it is intended for use in a warning system of some kind. This split can be seen in the distinction between segmented and operational data, as described by Ahmed et al [11]. Segmented data is data that classifies "flaring" data points as having a flare occur within the following 24 hours, and "non-flaring" data points as not having a flare in the ± 48 hours surrounding a data point [11]. This means discarding any data points that were observed 24-48 hours before a flare. By segmenting data this way, it provides the model with a stronger distinction between positive and negative events, which should improve its performance. In an operational setting, the positive flares are classified the same way, but a negative data point is merely defined as not having a flare occur in the following 24 hours[11]. A segmented data set allows for feature analysis of a more effective model, and is therefore suited for a theoretical research setting. However, in practice, it is not possible to discard data points that do not fit your data paradigm. Every data point has to be classified in some way as "flaring" or "non-flaring."

In addition to machine learning models, there are several researchers who created statistical methods, such as methods that use the McIntosh classification. Bloomfield et al created a Poisson flare distribution to connect the McIntosh classification of an AR to yes/no predictions of solar flares [12]. This method found that the maximum TSS for forecasting M-class flares was 0.457, with a threshold value of 20%, where the method predicts "flare" for probabilities about the threshold[12].

A key paper within the machine learning sphere was written by Bobra and Couvidat, where they trained an SVM model on SHARPs data [6]. They also did feature analysis and feature engineering to create additional features for their model, including quantities like the flux within the polarity inversion line[6]. They ranked each feature by usefulness using F-scores to determine their relationship to flaring and non-flaring data points. They do not perform any kind of correlation analysis, as a SVM is not sensitive to highly correlated features. In addition, they explore their model's performance on both operational and segmented data sets, and found as expected that it performs better on the segmented data. For predicting solar flares with a magnitude $>M1.0$, their model has a TSS of 0.82 in segmented mode and a TSS of 0.76 in operational mode[6]. However, they note that the model has a high number of false positives.

Although SVM is a popular machine learning model within solar flare prediction, it is not the only one that has been studied. In particular, a paper by Nishizuka et al compared SVM, KNN, and extremely randomized trees (ERT)

[13]. Rather than using SHARPs parameters like Bobra and Couvidat, they calculated their own parameters from magnetograms and the UV Continuum recorded by AIA. In addition, rather than using the ARs calculated by the HMI team or those found by NOAA, they determined their own ARs for analysis by analyzing the full-disk magnetograms and selecting areas of interest. From these active regions, they extracted features such as the area, the magnetic flux, and the number of magnetic neutral lines [13]. They also calculated features used by Bobra and Couvidat, including the vertical current and the Lorenz force. Finally, they included the novel feature of UV brightening calculated from AIA UV Continuums. It is difficult to compare this methodology with other models, because Nishizuka et al used such different procedures and were working with different data. For predicting $>M1.0$ class flares, their models had a TSS = 0.912 for KNN, TSS = 0.87 for SVM, and TSS = 0.82 for ERT[13].

These results do seem much higher than other models, but it is important to note that to calculate this TSS, Nishizuka et al used a machine learning method called cross-validation. This partitions the data set into validation and training sets multiple times to compare the model against the entire data set and make sure no overfitting is occurring. However, the method they used is known as "shuffle and split" cross validation, meaning the data set is shuffled before being split into training and validation sets. Since they did not make sure that the entire observed period of a particular AR exists exclusively in the training or validation set, it is possible that these high scores come from the model having future knowledge. If an AR has 10 data points recorded over the course of several days, then the validation set would get 3 of those data points to classify. However, the training set has future knowledge of the AR, since the data points are selected at random and it is unlikely that all three data points would occur last. Therefore, from an operational standpoint, these TSS values are not telling the full picture. In a later paper[14], they list the results in an operational setting, where they used data from 2010-2014 for training and data from 2015 for validation. In this setting, they had a TSS of 0.33 for their SVM, 0.19 for their KNN, and 0.17 for the ERT [14]. Although the differences in data sets and classifications have the same problems with comparison, these numbers are more appropriate for comparison in an operational setting.

For reasons like the ones listed above, comparing different methods that use different data and different validation methods is very difficult. Therefore, it is worthwhile to compare methods using the same data and the same validation methods to see if any actually stand out. There was a workshop held in 2009

to compare the results from different prediction methods using all the same data sources. The data set was magnetograms and continuum diagrams from SOHO/MDI, from 2000-2005. The ARs were defined to match with NOAA, with a method for combining physically close ARs together. To evaluate the methods, several skill scores were calculated, including ApSS and TSS. Models included both statistical methods and machine learning methods. Of the methods discussed so far, only the statistical method from Bloomfield et al was included in this comparison. It was found that no particular model performed better on the provided data than any other, despite having models ranging from simple statistical ones to advanced machine learning[5].

Although most machine learning research in this subject has looked into methods like SVM models, there has been investigation into using a deep neural net. Nishizuka et al developed a deep neural net model, using their parameters and active region detection model from their comparison of KNN, SVM, and ERT models. They once again used images from SDO, from 2010-2015. Their model output probabilities for each level of flare prediction, rather than predicting yes/no for a flare[14]. They also tested their model in an operational setting, thus avoiding the problems discussed with their previous model's use of cross-validation. With their neural net, they got a TSS of 0.80, much better than the operational results from their SVM model [14].

4.1 Previous Work at LASP

In my previous work in this subject, we focused on using deep learning with neural networks. My team looked at a few different kinds of models, including Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) recurrent neural nets, the usual Multi-layer perceptron (MLP) neural net, and a Convolutional Neural Net (CNN) for analyzing images. For our data sets, we used the SHARPs parameters plus our own features for the two scalar models and magnetograms from HMI for the CNN. To label the data sets, we used GOES X-ray data to classify data points as "positive" if they had an M-class flare within the following 24 hours, and "negative" if they did not have an M-class flare in the following 24 hours. Note that we only analyzed the operational style of data, and did not look at segmented data, unlike Bobra and Couvidat and Ahmed et al. The LSTM model was intended to capture the evolution of an AR over time, as a recurrent neural net can take information from previous iterations over a data point and use that as a memory to influence the results of the current data point. An LSTM

introduces "gates" which allow for the deletion of the previous states. So, information from the same AR would carry over through data points recorded at different times, but the state would be deleted and the information from each AR would be separate. Using an LSTM, we got a TSS of 0.76. However, by training an MLP, we were able to get a TSS of 0.90, meaning the model that was most accurate was one that did not take previous data from an AR into account. The MLP model also did not use any features beyond the SHARPs parameters, as feature engineering was taking place in parallel.

While these models were being developed, we also worked on feature engineering, to capture important information found by other papers to improve models. To take into account the history of the region, we calculated features about the previous flares experienced within an AR, including the number, average duration, and number of seconds since the most recent. In addition, we applied feature analysis to the SHARPs parameters and to the flare history features calculated, using an ANOVA F-test to rank the features by usefulness. Our results agreed with Bobra and Couvidat's feature analysis, although the ranking did not perfectly line up. In our analysis, the flare history features ended up being important. When compared to the rest of the SHARPs parameters, 3 of the flare history parameters ended up in the top 10 most valuable features. In addition to the flare history parameters, we have been working to get polarity inversion lines as a feature. Polarity inversion lines are another feature that turns up in many models, as they describe aspects about how much magnetic field is captured in an AR. The feature analysis on that feature is not completed.

Finally, the magnetograms of different ARs were analyzed using a CNN. A CNN is a specialized neural net for analyzing images. Our model uses vector magnetograms, and outputs probabilities for flaring/non-flaring within 24 hours. To train this CNN, we used a method known as "transfer learning," where we use weights from a neural net for classifying general images. These weights are for the first part of the CNN, where the image data is condensed into key features. Then, the solar flare classification training occurs on the output of the CNN by using the features from the convolving and filtering steps to train a classifier. Using this method, we got a TSS of 0.97.

5 Methodology

The vast majority of previous work in this area has been focused on individual sunspot analysis. However, solar dynamics are not limited to a single AR. Restricting analysis to only individual ARs could be eliminating data from the interactions between multiple ARs. This work focuses on these interactions by looking at full disk data and creating features based on networks of ARs.

The Sun goes through eleven year cycles of activity, where there are more sunspots and therefore more solar flares and CMEs during high periods in the cycle. Sunspots cluster closer to the equator during low periods in the cycle. This can be seen in a plot known as a butterfly diagram, which uses time along the X axis and the latitude along the Y axis to plot sunspot area.

Figure 1: Butterfly diagram created from observations from Royal Greenwich Observatory[15]

Figure 1 indicates that there could be a correlation between the distance from the Sun's equator and the magnetic energy that emerges through ARs.

An active region is caused by the highly turbulent magnetic layer known as the *convection layer* that lies below the photosphere (the visible surface). When loops of magnetic energy break through the surface, they push aside the hot plasma. This is why sunspots appear dark on images of the solar disk - in reality, they are very bright, but are much cooler than the solar surface[15]. The

existence of ARs depends on the internal mechanics of the Sun. Scientists have modelled these internal dynamics, and inferred information about them using sound waves with helioseismology, but they can not be directly observed. Data about the convection layer hasn't been included in previous works on feature engineering despite its undisputed importance on the changes in magnetic energy for this reason. However, I think it is possible to infer some information about the convection layer from full-disk photosphere data such as magnetograms.

To do this analysis, I created networks of sunspots and calculated features relating to their distances and interactions. I was attempting to capture some of the subsurface dynamics which create sunspots and cause solar flares and CMEs. By using a network, I could leverage existing algorithms which explore relationships between nodes in a system. However, a network does not accurately capture the interactions between ARs, as the information does not flow through single lines of communication between ARs but underneath them in a complicated magnetic system. The use of networks is not intended to fully capture that complexity, but to provide a framework that I could use to explore full disk analysis and create a basic model of the relationships between ARs. The features I created were based primarily on distance. Since magnetic flux decreases proportionally to distance, this seemed like a key factor in the relationship between two ARs, and one I wanted to capture. Therefore, I focused most of my energy on determining the efficacy of using networks for analysis and to do a broad study of different features that network analysis provides.

5.1 Coordinate Systems

The first step in doing distance analysis is determining what coordinate system will be the most effective for calculation. On Earth, the usual coordinate system is latitude and longitude, which mark out lines on the surface of Earth and classify any point on its surface. However, in space science, coordinate systems are complicated by our point of view. It may seem easiest to use a fixed coordinate system for the Solar surface, like on Earth, so a given point always has the same latitude and longitude. In some cases, however, the objective location on the Sun's surface is less important than the subjective position of a location with regards to Earth.

Heliographic Stonyhurst coordinates are based on the second idea. It defines a latitude/longitude coordinate system projected onto the solar surface as seen from Earth. The Sun then rotates underneath. This means that a given spot

on the solar surface changes coordinates as the Sun rotates, but an area directly facing Earth will always have the same latitude and longitude[16].

Figure 2: Heliographic Stonyhurst coordinate system [17]

The data from HMI has location in Heliographic Stonyhurst coordinates. For my features, I need a coordinate system that describes the same spot the same way over time and can be used to determine distance between two ARs. Therefore, the ideal coordinate system is *Carrington Heliographic*. The whole coordinate system rotates as the Sun does, so each point is described with the same coordinates. To convert the data from Heliographic Stonyhurst to Carrington Heliographic, I use the SkyCoord Python package. SkyCoord is part of Astropy, and can be used to convert between different coordinate systems as well as calculating distance between two points. This distance calculation is also what I used to compute the distance between ARs and create networks.

5.2 Creating Networks

To create the networks, I pulled all existing ARs for a given time step and calculated the distances of all ARs to each other. I started with a fully connected graph, where every node is connected to every other node. The edges of this graph are weighted by distance.

This kind of fully connected network is not particularly useful. In particular, I am interested in the structure of the graph, since the edges do not represent any kind of information transfer. Most structural network analysis depends on the way nodes are connected, not on the weighted edges. To conduct analysis on the graph I removed edges above a certain weight. Any ARs that are further

Figure 3: A fully connected network of ARs on the Sun's surface

apart than the threshold distance are disconnected, which can also result in several unconnected components.

The threshold of the network is not determined by a known physical process. That is, there is no scientific spot where no information is transferred between ARs of a certain distance. Therefore, thresholds for the network must be determined empirically, and it is entirely possible that features calculated using this data would be better served with a different threshold. However, to explore the kinds of analysis using networks provides, I focused on using a threshold at the mean distance of all ARs. This threshold allows for the elimination of edges between ARs that are very distant, while preserving the majority of edges between nearby ARs. In addition, if there are two or more very separated components, this threshold generally leaves them separated, or at least be connected by very few edges. In addition, I created ten evenly spaced thresholds to explore different levels of connectivity in the network.

It is important to note that a threshold adds another degree of uncertainty to any computed features. Although the mean threshold is a fairly good way of separating components, in the future, it would be better to have features weighted by the distance instead of trying to cut the graph up into thresholds.

Figure 4: A network of ARs on the Sun's surface thresholded by mean distance.

Once the networks for each time step are created, I calculated my features and added them to the existing data. So, every AR that was part of the network has network features, in addition to the SHARPs parameters that were created.

5.3 Created Features

I created eight features based on networks which capture some element of the structure of ARs on the Solar surface. Most of these features are unique for networks with different thresholds, so additional features can be created with different thresholds for the network.

Flare_in_component is a feature which attempts to capture the energy contained in a component of the graph. The flux in an AR is often an effective feature for flare prediction, as it indicates the level of magnetic energy in the system [6]. Since most solar dynamics occur below the photosphere, my reasoning was nearby ARs that have enough energy to flare are sharing that energy with nearby ARs.

However, a component in a network is not the best way to compare distance, because it is possible that evenly-spaced ARs could span the solar surface but

flare_in_component	A boolean value to indicate if there was a flare in the same component during the same time period
mean_distance	The average distance between ARs
closest_dist	The smallest distance between ARs
hc_lat	The latitude of the location in Carrington Heliographic coordinates
hc_lon	The Y coordinate of the location in Carrington Heliographic coordinates
total_nodes	The total count of nodes (ARs) in the network
eig_centrality	The Eigenvector Centrality measure of the node in the network
centrality_ratio	The ratio of centrality of the node over the number of nodes in the component

be in a single component. In this case, the flare in component feature may still be useful for prediction, but it would not be because of nearby energy.

The next two features, *mean_distance* and *closest_dist* are statistics about the general spacing of ARs. I added these two features because a time step where ARs are closely grouped together could have more energy in the system and the distance of all ARs could be a good indication of flaring.

hc_lat and *hc_lon* contain the coordinates in latitude and longitude of the AR in Carrington Heliographic coordinates. Carrington Heliographic coordinates rotate with an approximation of the Sun’s rotation[16]. These points are fixed on the surface of the Sun, so these features capture the objective position of an AR.

total_nodes contains information about the size of the network. This is a count of the total ARs at the given time point. This has information about the complexity of the solar dynamics occurring. It also allows for comparison about the size of the component compared to the total size of the network.

eig_centrality is a measurement of the Eigenvector centrality of the node. This measures a node’s place in the structure of the graph, and provides information about its importance in the transference of information. The algorithm used comes from the NetworkX library.

Finally, *centrality_ratio* takes the centrality measure computed in the previous feature and divides it by the total number of nodes in the network. Here, I wanted to eliminate any bias that comes from being in a smaller component and make centrality a more objective measurement.

Most of these features change with the threshold of the distance graph. To try and capture the way these features change, and to do a broad stroke check

of the effectiveness of a feature, I computed them for a range of thresholds, starting with the smallest distance and splitting into ten even pieces up to the largest distance. I also computed these values for the mean threshold, to see if that single threshold was as effective as the rest. Therefore, I ended up with 100 features, including 20 features from the SHARPs dataset. After removing any rows with NaN values and assigning "0" to any missing values, I had 227,200 data points to use in analysis.

6 Results

To compute results, I used two different methods to evaluate the effectiveness of the network features compared to the existing SHARPs parameters. First, I used a F-test upon scaled data to come up with a statistical ranking of features that compare the difference between flaring and non flaring data to determine importance. However, using this method only looks at the differences in populations for each individual feature, and does not show how these features interact with each other in the much more complex neural net. Therefore, I also trained several multi-layer perceptron (MLP) neural nets using different parameters for hidden layer count to explore how these features compare to a model only using SHARPs parameters.

6.1 Feature Ranking

Feature ranking involves a relative comparison of all the features to discover which features have a significant difference between flaring and non-flaring populations. Features with a large difference in flaring and non-flaring populations theoretically can result in better prediction. An effective feature can be expanded on and explored to discover why it works well and to find additional features that may be related and improve the model as a whole.

I performed statistical feature analysis using an F-test to compute scores for all features, including my custom features and the features that come pre-computed as part of the SHARPs dataset. I include all previous features to compare the effectiveness to my unique features to that of features commonly used in flare prediction and that are known to correlate with flaring populations. To scale the features, I used sklearn's *robust_scale*. Since the F-test depends on the difference between populations, using unscaled data gives features that are on a larger scale an advantage. For instance, the feature *USFLUX*, which

describes the total unsigned flux of an AR, has an average value of $1.156 * 10^{22}$. Even if a difference of 100 is small compared to the scale of that data point, it is a much larger difference than any difference between the count of ARs, which has a mean of 0.99. Any test that uses the objective difference between datapoints will favor features that exist on that larger scale. Therefore, scaling the features will give us a better evaluation of all the features together. *Robust_scale* scales by centering the data and by scaling it to unit variance.

When I computed the F-test using unscaled data, none of my features were in the top 10 and only one was above the HARPNUM feature. The HARPNUM feature is completely unrelated to flaring, as it is assigned to ARs as an identification number and is completely unrelated to their physical properties. Therefore, it can be used as a useful indicator of the level of random noise. Any features that fall below HARPNUM are unrelated to flaring.

To process this data, I first scaled the data within each feature, so it was centered and scaled to the variance of each feature. Then, I scaled the entire dataset, so every data point was centered and scaled around the universal variance. Every feature is between -1 and 1. Then, I computed another F-test on the scaled data.

Eigenvector Centrality (9, 8, 7, 6)
Connected Components (9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3)
Eigenvector Centrality (2)
Centrality Ratio (2)
Eigenvector Centrality (5)
Nodes in Component (3)
Centrality Ratio (6, 5, 4)
Eigenvector Centrality (4)
Centrality Ratio (7)

Table 1: Top performing features in F-test. The thresholds are put in parentheses after the feature name, in order from best to worst. The threshold goes from 0, the smallest, to 9, the largest.

After scaling, the top ten features were all my features. The top four were Eigenvector centralities at different thresholds, and the lower six were the count of the number of nodes in the connected component at different thresholds. The top value was the eigenvector centrality of the largest threshold, and the rest of the top ten features also had high thresholds.

In the top half of the feature ranking, all the top values were from my custom values, with seven SHARPs parameters coming in just before the break

between top half and bottom half. The SHARPs parameters were ordered in a very similar way to previous analyses, including the feature analysis conducted by Bobra and Couvidat[6], which is a good indication that the feature analysis is accurate.

Other consistently high-scoring parameters, with different threshold levels, include the centrality ratio and the count of nodes in component. It seems that the structure of a graph does have a difference in flaring and non-flaring populations, so my hypotheses about network analysis have merit. Interestingly, the ratings of thresholds for different features differ. While a larger threshold results in a better score for the centrality and the count of nodes in the component, the higher-scoring values of the centrality ratio fall in the middle of the threshold range. This is a result I was not expecting, as it indicates the threshold for graph creation is more important than I anticipated. A certain threshold can result in better results for some features, but not others. This makes determining a good threshold both very important and much more difficult.

The lowest scoring features are the `flare_in_component` feature at all different thresholds. They start at the bottom with the smallest threshold, and go up uninterrupted in order to the highest threshold, with the mean threshold at the top. This result is so surprising it actually indicates to me that there could be a problem with the data or the way the feature was calculated, since it seems unlikely that the effectiveness would exactly follow the order that the data points were organized in the dataset. Regardless, if the flare in component feature is actually such a low performer, maybe the structure of the graph does not indicate anything about the energy of the system. On the other hand, it could just be that there is a much better feature that can compute energy, and this specific method is ineffective.

The location features `hc_lat` and `hc_lon` were also poor performers. `hc_lat` scored much higher than `hc_lon`, which is a result I was expecting based on the butterfly diagram, but both scored well below the randomly assigned HARP-`NUM` parameter. It seems location does not correlate well with flaring. The scaling of such different forms of data has a sensitivity to machine numerical errors, and the final way to determine feature importance is in training machine learning models using the features. From a purely theoretical standpoint, however, several of my custom features scored well in the F-test.

6.2 Model Creation

To test feature performance in an operational setting, I trained several MLP neural nets on data that contained only the SHARPs parameters and on data that contained subsets of the custom features to compare accuracy.

Although training models gives a better idea about the performance of features, it does not allow for fine-tuned ranking of features in the same way the F-test does. In addition, neural networks can depend heavily on specific tuning towards data, which involves adjusting the equations and tolerances that create the model for a more accurate system. I have done very little of this tuning, by only looking at a few different layer configurations rather than focusing on making one model accurate. The layer configuration is the number of hidden layers within the neural network which create the structure of the network. There are different configurations that can affect accuracy, but in general, the higher the count of hidden nodes, the more complicated the network.

I trained both the custom features dataset and the SHARPs dataset on identical models and then looked at the difference in the TSS scores between the two models. It is my hope that by doing an evaluation on a few different feature sets and by training many models, I can get a more accurate picture of the performance of features in a general case. However, it is difficult to predict features that will always work in all models, and any of these features could perform better or worse under different scenarios.

With that rather large caveat, I can show how the different subsets performed when compared to the SHARPs feature set. I looked at 3 different datasets: all the custom features included, only the top half of the custom features included, and the top ten best performing features included. All feature sets included the SHARPs parameters.

To compute these values, I used a model that was created with five different layer configurations, to see how the features performed in different contexts. I trained 20 models with each configuration on the data and averaged the TSS of each, to eliminate some of the random variance that can occur between models of identical setup and data. To get models that would predict anything besides false, I also had to undersample the non-flaring population. Undersampling is a technique to balance unbalanced datasets, like those for solar flares, by matching the number of flaring and non-flaring data points. I take a count of flaring data points and sample randomly from the non-flaring points until I have an equal number, before shuffling them. My validation dataset to compute TSS values

was not undersampled, and acted as unbalanced operational data. Every model used the same dataset. Once I undersampled the data, I was able to get a TSS above zero, usually around 0.3. However, the comparison is what is important, not the actual number.

Figure 5: Graph showing results of model analysis by comparing the TSS score of models trained with the custom features to identical models trained only on SHARPs data.

As shown by Figure 5, the models are nearly identical in TSS scores. They are close enough that in general, I do not think my features provided a marked improvement when included with SHARPs parameters. Interestingly, the scores for models trained with the top half of features consistently score better than either all features or only the top 10 features. It could be that since the top 10 features only include two network measurements at different thresholds, the models that only use them are hurt by the lack of additional information about the networks.

I also found it unusual that the average TSS scores for the SHARPS data are so different. The data is identical, so model structure might have a bigger factor on performance than I thought. In this case, the comparison of network features to SHARPs features within the models will show effectiveness more accurately than comparing against different model structures. Within the last two models, which had a single hidden layer of 600 nodes and two hidden layers with 500 nodes respectively, the network features do significantly better than the SHARPs data set. However, this improvement is not consistent. In the 600

node model only the top-half subset does better, and in the (500, 500) model the top-10 and complete data does better while the top-half subset is equal to the SHARPs data.

Ultimately, the model analysis is inconclusive. The best I can definitively say is my custom features did not significantly decrease the prediction power of the model, which is still a good result in feature engineering. There is some indication that more powerful models work better with network features, which is also positive, as it indicates that my model analysis could be incorrectly focused, not necessarily that the techniques I developed are flawed. In the end, the only way to truly know if a feature will improve the accuracy of a model is to implement it in the model.

7 Future Work

These features are just scratching the surface of the potential well of features this style of analysis provides. Both the full-disk analysis and the network data structure have great potential for additional feature creation in flare forecasting.

Full-disk features have not been used in existing research for flare-prediction. I mostly used them to create networks, but the most promising results came from the structure of the graph. Focusing more on the distance between ARs removes the difficulty of thresholding the network, and could make up for areas where the network structure was weak. For example, my feature to capture nearby flares within the network was the worst scoring feature in my feature set. However, if this feature still has useful dynamics, full-disk analysis could use a weighted average to compare the flare strength with the distance to existing ARs, providing more information than the binary number I used in that feature. Additionally, full-disk analysis that particularly attempts to capture full-disk dynamics could provide a lot of inferred information about the overall solar system to a prediction model.

Even the specific application of network analysis to full-disk analysis has a lot more to offer. The network of ARs on the solar surface is actually a *dynamic network*, where both nodes (ARs) and edges (thresholded distances) are created and destroyed over time. Dynamic networks are at the cutting edge of network science research. This particular application of dynamic networks is interesting for a number of reasons, including the low number of nodes, the hidden dynamics of the convection zone and the difficulty of thresholding. Although dynamic

networks are difficult to analyze, it has been shown that the history of flaring in an AR is an excellent indicator of future flaring, so the application of dynamic networks could yield very effective features.

Even static, full-disk networks have areas that would benefit from additional analysis. By modifying the structure, networks can capture a lot more than just the distance between ARs. For example, a network could capture the flow of magnetic energy by weighting edges by differences in flux between ARs instead of weighting by distance. In addition, exploring different thresholds could refine what features are particularly important.

Ultimately, flare prediction is a complex problem which benefits greatly from cross-disciplinary analysis. Analysis techniques from math and computer science have already increased the accuracy of flare prediction models. The system of solar dynamics is so complex that the best minds in solar science are unable to accurately predict solar weather. However, by bringing in people from different fields, we can gradually improve our prediction capabilities until a solar flare report will be as accurate as predicting the weather on Earth.

8 Conclusion

Ultimately, the analysis I conducted lacks the depth to conclusively say the features I developed will be effective for the majority of machine learning models. However, initial analyses show that creating features through full-disk networks has the potential to be a useful addition to model creation. In addition, the novel technique of full disk AR analysis provides information that single AR analysis lacks. In the field of flare prediction, the data that can be computed from magnetograms and other sources of solar data is extremely important. The lack of concrete information about the convection layer and the internal solar dynamics that cause solar flares is a big handicap when developing models that depend so heavily on the available data.

Through methods like this, it is possible to infer some of the missing important data, and techniques like network analysis can provide interesting information about relationships. This analysis can also be applied in individual ARs, and has the potential to provide much more information than what I looked into.

Through applying novel analysis techniques and drawing from different disciplines, we have already been making great strides in prediction and achieved

impressive initial results. 100 years ago, weather was an impossibly complex system that we never thought we could predict. Now weather prediction is a thriving field that has made great strides, both technologically and scientifically. As space weather prediction grows more important, it is my hope that we will continue to improve until solar flare prediction is as mundane as the sunrise.

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